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Abstract

This study investigates the form, frequency, severity, and perceived justice of parental corporal punishment and its relationship to negative personality dispositions among adolescents in Bangladesh. Data were collected from a sample of 500 students aged 10 to 18 years using the youth version of the Physical Punishment Questionnaire (for mothers and fathers separately) and the child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire. Descriptive and correlational analyses indicated that "slapping" was the most common form of punishment. Results revealed that increased frequency, severity, and perceived injustice of parental corporal punishment significantly correlate with higher levels of psychological maladjustment, emotional unresponsiveness, impaired self-esteem, and a negative worldview in adolescents. Furthermore, the study noted significant gender dynamics: mothers administered punishment more frequently than fathers, and male children experienced higher rates of corporal punishment than their female counterparts.

Corporal Punishment by Parents and Negative Personality Dispositions in Adolescents of Bangladesh

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This study mainly explored form, frequency, severity, and other aspects of corporal punishment experienced by children at the hands of their parents and their possible relations to a constellation of seven personality dispositions of adolescents. Additionally, it examined whether punishment experiences and personality dispositions varied by gender of children and whether punishment practices varied by gender of parents. Data were collected by administering the youth version of the Physical Punishment Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers, the child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire, and the Personal Information Form on a sample of 500 students between the ages of 10 to 18 years. Percentage analyses revealed that adolescents listed "slapping" as the most common form of corporal punishment and "kneeling" as the least common form. Percentage analyses further revealed that about 50% of the adolescents reported their punishment as occurring "occasionally/often/very often"; more than 50% of the adolescents perceived the punishment as "hard". Analyses revealed that i) males experienced more form, frequency, severity, and incidence of paternal (but not maternal) punishment than females, ii) mothers punished children with more form, frequency, harshness, immediacy, consistency, predictability, and incidence than did fathers, iii) the more the form, frequency, and severity of punishment children experienced with at the hands of their parents especially mothers, the more overall psychologically maladjusted, aggressive, and emotionally unresponsive they were; and the more impaired self-esteem, impaired self-adequacy, and negative worldview they had. Significant correlations between other aspects of corporal punishment and personality dispositions were also observed.

Keywords: Corporal Punishment, Aggression, Dependence, Emotional Instability, Emotional Unresponsiveness, Impaired Self-esteem, Impaired Self-adequacy, Negative Worldview

Physical punishment is the use of direct or indirect infliction of physical discomfort or pain on a child by a person in a position of authority over the child (e.g., parent) usually for the purpose of (1) stopping a child's unwanted behavior, (2) preventing the reoccurrence of unwanted behavior, or (3) because the child failed to do something s/he was supposed to do (Rohner, 2005).

Common types of physical punishment are spanking and slapping. However, more severe forms of punishment such as beating or hitting may also be viewed as part of culturally acceptable physical punishment (Anderson & Payne, 1994; Arnold & Phil, 1982).

Physical punishment of children occurs globally (Ember & Ember, 2005). It takes place at home, in schools and

institutions, care systems, and on the streets. It is used in more than 75% of the world's societies at least "occasionally" (Barry, Josephson, Lauer, & Marshall, 1977; Ember & Ember, 2005; Levinson, 1989). Levinson (1981, 1989) showed that corporal punishment was used "frequently" in only 20% of the societies. More often, parents resort to other child-rearing techniques such as exhorting and setting an example of appropriate behavior, which were found in about 82% of the societies (Barry et al., 1977). Thus, it is clear that parents around the world tend to rely on a variety of strategies to discipline their children. Despite the fact that corporal punishment is used in all major regions of the world, its actual frequency of use varies across culture.

Parents in extended families tend to use corporal punishment less often than parents in nuclear families (Munroe & Munroe, 1980; Rohner, 1986). Parents in more complex societies are more likely to use corporal punishments than are parents in less complex society (Levinson, 1989). Ember and Ember (2005) suggested that frequent corporal punishments are likely to be found in societies that are marked by power inequality associated with the presence of social stratification, high levels of political hierarchy, or by an alien power and in most societies that practice warfare. Personal beliefs and cultural meanings are also associated with corporal punishment. For example, parents' beliefs in supernatural forces are linked to the frequency and severity of corporal punishment (Otterbein & Otterbein, 1973; Ritchie & Ritchie, 1981; Murphy-Cowan & Stringer, 2001).

An impressive body of research reported that corporal punishment carries with it negative baggage. For example, corporal punishment is associated with increased aggression in child and adolescent (e.g., Becker, 1964; Patterson, 1982; Steinmetz, 1979). Social information processing theories propose that corporal punishment may affect

a child's social-cognitive processes such that they evaluate aggression as an acceptable, effective form of problem-solving (Dodge, Pettit, McClaskey, & Brown, 1986). Corporal punishment appears to have a dampening effect on self-esteem in its victims. However, studies have been inconclusive and evidence-based literature in this area is much thinner (Paolucci & Violato, 2004).

Recently, Mathurin, Gielen, and Lancaster (2006) have examined different forms of corporal punishment as experienced by 155, 11- to 17-year-old youths in St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands. They reported that the greater the variety of forms of punishment males experienced, the more emotionally unstable, aggressive, and overall psychologically maladjusted they were. But no significant relation emerged between corporal punishment and personality variables for females. A small subgroup of highly punished females and males, however, reported more feelings of emotional instability, hostility, and overall psychological maladjustment than did less severely punished youths.

Though corporal punishment is a widely researched phenomenon, only a single survey is known to have been conducted so far addressing the issue of punishment in the cultural context of Bangladesh. The survey included 3840 children between the ages of 9 and 18 years (UNICEF, 2008). It has reported that nearly all children (97%) are punished at home and 74 percent receives corporal punishment at the hands of parents or guardians. About half of them receive corporal punishment at home 'frequently' or 'at times'. More than one third of the children reported that the frequency and severity of punishment were 'moderate to high'. The most common forms of punishment were scolding/rebuking/censuring/threatening (99.3%), slapping (69.9%) and beating/throwing things/kicking (39.7%). Mothers were more likely than fathers or other household members to punish children. Parents are less likely to use

corporal punishment when they have a higher level of education. According to the report, children voiced their concern about the emotional and physical harm of punishment and believed that punishment is not acceptable after a certain age or for minor infractions. On the whole, children perceived that corporal punishment does more harm than good.

It is evident from the UNICEF study that punishment is pervasively prevalent in Bangladesh. It is also known from the study that punishment is perceived negative by the victim concern. However, the study cannot answer the question of whether corporal punishment by parents is associated with personality traits in children of Bangladesh. Therefore, the main objective of the present study is to explore possible relations between corporal punishment experienced at the hands of parents and personality dispositions in adolescent children of Bangladesh.

METHOD

Sample

This research was conducted on a sample of 600, 6th through 10th grade students recruited from six schools of the capital city, Dhaka. While the schools were selected purposively the respondents within each school were selected conveniently. School-wise internal consistency reliability showed a particular school to have yielded unacceptably low alpha coefficient. Consequently, respondents of that school were excluded for further analyses. Thus, 500 respondents left for subsequent analyses. Their ages ranged from 10 to 18 years with a mean age being 13.64 years and a standard deviation of 1.66. An overwhelming majority (about 96%) of the respondents identified themselves to be middle class family backgrounds. Their parental education ranged from none to postgraduate levels. Eighty nine percent of the respondents' mothers were engaged in homemaking while 95% of their fathers were either in service (49%) or in business (46%). The details of other sample

characteristics are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1 about here

Measures

The present study required the following three questionnaires and a demographic form: (1 and 2) the youth version of the Physical Punishment Questionnaire for mothers and for fathers (PPQ: Youth); (3) the child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire (PAQ); and the Personal Information Form (PIF) for demographic information. Each measure is described more fully below.

PPQ. Bangla translated PPQ (Uddin, Zaman, & Semul, 2012) was used in the present study (originally developed by Rohner, Ripoll-Nunez, Moodier, & Ruan, 2005). It is a 26-item self-report questionnaire assessing youths' perceptions of their current experiences of corporal punishment. The measure contains a variety of response options used for different items. Children who were physically punished at the hands of their mothers (major female caregivers) and fathers (major male caregivers) were asked to make overall judgments about nine issues related to their experiences of corporal punishment. These issues are (a) overall frequency of punishment received (i.e. how often was the respondent punished?); (b) overall severity of punishment received (i.e. how hard or severe does the punishment tend to be?); (c) consistency of punishment (i.e. does the caregiver sometimes punish a given misbehavior and sometimes not?); (d) predictability of punishment received (i.e. when respondents are punished, can they tell or predict from one time to another whether they will be punished?); (e) overall incidents of punishment received (i.e. how many times in any given week does the respondent tend to be punished?); (f) perceived fairness of punishment received (i.e. as a general rule, to what extent does the respondent feel the punishment is fair?); (g) perceived deservedness of punishment received (i.e. as

Table 1
Distribution of respondents by selected demographic, personal, and social variables
(N = 500)

Variable	N	%
Respondent's Gender		
Male	254	50.8
Female	246	49.2
Academic Grade		
Six	106	21.2
Seven	102	20.4
Eight	99	19.8
Nine	96	19.2
Ten	97	19.4
Socioeconomic Class		
Lower Class	8	1.6
Middle Class	482	96.4
Upper Class	10	2.0
Maternal Education		
Illiterate	17	3.4
Primary	174	34.8
Secondary	139	27.8
Higher Secondary	73	14.6
Graduate	54	10.8
Masters	43	8.6
Paternal Education		
Illiterate	8	1.6
Primary	71	14.2
Secondary	87	17.4
Higher Secondary	140	28.0
Graduate	94	18.8
Masters	89	17.8
PhD	11	2.2
Maternal Occupation		
Homemaking	446	89.2
Service	54	10.8
Paternal Occupation		
Service	245	49.0
Business	230	46.0
Labor	10	2.0
Farmer	15	3.0

a general rule, to what extent does the respondent feel the punishment is deserved?); (h) timing of punishment received (i.e. is the punishment administered at the moment the parent discovered the youth has done something wrong, or is it delayed for a period of time?); and (i) parents use of explanation or reasoning (i.e. to what extent does the caregiver explain to the youth before punishing them what they did that was wrong and why it was wrong?).

The PPQ, in addition to these nine theoretical issues, asks about 13 more specific forms of punishment that they may have experienced at least once. These are spanking, slapping, shoving, yanking, kicking, beating (severely with an object that leaves a mark, welt, or bruise), hitting (firmly but not severely with an object that leaves no mark, welt or bruise), pulling (hair), twisting (ear), kneeling, standing, pinching, and shaking. The questionnaire additionally asks

respondents to volunteer up to four other forms of punishment they may have experienced at least once.

Frequency of punishment correlates positively with severity of punishment in most studies. Similarly, fairness and deservedness of punishment generally correlate positively. Researchers sum the two scores to create a composite measure of perceived harshness and justness (which can spread from a low of 2 through a high of 9, from a low of 2 through a high of 8, respectively) of punishment. The higher the score is on the harshness and the justness variables, youths perceive the punishment to be harsher and more just respectively. Alpha coefficients for the portion of study were .55 and .62 for maternal and paternal harshness; .33 and .45 for maternal and paternal justness.

PAQ. Bangla translated child PAQ (Uddin & Ahmed, 2012) was used to measure youths' overall psychological adjustment. The child version of the Personality Assessment Questionnaire is a 42-item self-report questionnaire assessing the form of psychological adjustment-maladjustment (Rohner & Khaleque, 2005). This form of psychological adjustment (or maladjustment) is defined by seven personality dispositions measured on the PAQ. These include: (1) hostility/aggression, passive aggression, or problems with the management of hostility and aggression; (2) dependence or defensive independence; (3) feelings of impaired self-esteem; (4) feelings of impaired self-adequacy; (5) emotional unresponsiveness; (6) emotional instability; and (7) negative worldview. The PAQ has been used successfully in several hundred studies internationally, and it has been shown to have excellent reliability and validity for use in cross-cultural research (Khaleque & Rohner, 2002; Rohner & Khaleque, 2005).

Some of the sample items on the measure are "I think about fighting or being unkind" (hostility or aggression); " I like myself" (positive self-esteem); "I can compete successfully for the things I want" (positive

self-adequacy); "It's easy for me to show my friends that I really like them" (emotional responsiveness); "I am cheerful and happy one minute and gloomy or unhappy the next" (emotional instability); "I think the world is a good, happy place" (positive worldview). The child PAQ, which is available in more than 20 languages, has been used in many studies cross-culturally. From these studies, a large body of evidence summarized in Rohner and Khaleque (2005) showing the measure to be reliable and valid for use in cross-cultural research. Coefficient alpha for the current study was .70.

PIF. The PIF elicited demographic, personal, and social information that included respondent's gender, age, grade in school, academic achievement, number of siblings, birth order, family size, parental education, parental occupation, family socioeconomic status, religious affiliation, etc.

Procedure

A written permission prior to collecting data was requested and received from principals of respective schools. Following permission, questionnaires and the PIF attached to the top of the questionnaires were administered in classroom settings. Before the administration, necessary rapport was established with respondents. Respondents completed the questionnaires at their own paces. The respondents were assured that their responses will be kept confidential and that there is nothing like right or wrong responses to any question. Finally, respondents were encouraged to ask questions coming in their minds during the task and they were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. On average, respondents spent one hour to complete the task. Every respondent was thanked and given a gift for his participation.

Results

We performed both descriptive and inferential statistics using SPSS 11.5 version in Window based environment. Descriptive statistics involved mean, standard deviation,

frequency, percentage, and correlation; inferential statistics involved independent and paired t tests. To arrange common forms of punishment in descending order, we computed frequency and percentage for different forms and presented them in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 about here

As evident in Table 2.1, the most common form of parental punishment listed

was "slapping" (73.6% for fathers and 83.6% for mothers) and the least form was "kneeling" (19.8% for fathers and 23.4% for mothers) for the whole sample. The similar trends were also observed for boys and girls. Slapping was followed by 'standing' by father and 'pulling hair' by mother. Third in descending order is 'pulling hair' by father and 'twisting ear' by mother.

To assess frequency, severity, consistency, predictability, incidence,

Table 2.1

Frequency (%) of forms of paternal and maternal punishment for total sample (N = 500), boys (N = 254), and girls (N = 246)

Forms	Paternal Punishment			Forms	Maternal Punishment		
	Boys	Girls	Total		Boys	Girls	Total
Slap	197(77.6)	171(69.5)	368(73.6)	Slap	206(81.1)	212(86.2)	418(83.6)
Stand	125 (49.2)	106(43.1)	231(46.2)	Hair Pull	168(66.1)	159(64.6)	327(65.4)
Hair Pull	118 (46.5)	94(38.2)	212(42.4)	Ear Twist	150(59.1)	142(57.7)	292(58.4)
Ear Twist	110 (43.3)	100(40.7)	210(42.0)	Shoves	122(48.0)	145(58.9)	267(53.4)
Hits	105(41.3)	88(35.8)	193(38.60)	Hits	133(52.4)	110(47.7)	243(48.6)
Shakes	98 (38.6)	88(35.8)	186(37.2)	Shakes	122(48.0)	97(39.8)	219(43.8)
Shoves	93 (36.6)	88(35.8)	181(36.2)	Beats	116(45.7)	90(36.6)	206(41.2)
Spank	75 (29.5)	96(39.0)	171(34.2)	Kicks	107(42.1)	99(40.2)	206(41.2)
Yanks	83 (32.7)	71(28.9)	154(30.8)	Yanks	104(40.9)	99(40.2)	203(40.6)
Pinches	78 (30.7)	68(27.6)	146(29.2)	Spank	95 (37.4)	104(42.3)	199(39.8)
Kicks	80 (31.5)	62(25.2)	142(28.4)	Pinches	102(40.2)	93(37.8)	195(39.0)
Beats	76 (29.9)	58(23.6)	134(26.8)	Stand	107(42.1)	86(35.0)	193(38.6)
Kneel	57 (22.4)	42(17.1)	99(19.8)	Kneel	60(23.6)	57(23.2)	117(23.4)

fairness, deservedness, latency, and explanation of punishment, we further computed frequency and percentage for each

category of responses to nine different aspects of physical punishment and presented them in Tables 2.2 through 2.10.

Table 2.2

Frequency (%) of responses to "Overall, my father/mother punishes me -----"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Only once or twice	48(18.9)	72(29.2)	120(24.0)	42(16.5)	45(18.3)	87(17.4)
Not often	56(22.1)	76(30.9)	132(26.4)	35(13.8)	44(17.9)	79(15.8)
Occasionally	107(42.1)	76(30.9)	183(36.6)	95(37.4)	86(35.0)	181(36.2)
Fairly often	12(4.7)	4(1.8)	16(3.2)	33(13.0)	40(16.2)	73(14.6)
Very often	31(12.2)	18(7.2)	49(9.8)	49(19.3)	31(12.6)	80(16.0)

As shown in Table 2.2, 49.6% and 66.8% of the adolescents reported respectively for their paternal and maternal punishment as occurring occasionally or so when the frequency of punishment categories 'occasionally', 'fairly often' and 'very often' were

combined. Findings also showed that more females reported their frequency of parental punishment as occurring less often (60.1% for fathers and 36.2% for mothers) than did males (41% for fathers and 30.3% for mothers).

Table 2.3

Frequency (%) of responses to "Overall, when my father/mother punishes me it is -----"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Not hard at all	47(18.5)	69(28.1)	116(23.2)	51(20.1)	44(17.9)	95(19.0)
Not very hard	39(15.4)	42(17.1)	81(16.2)	52(20.5)	39(15.9)	91(18.2)
A little hard	121(47.6)	97(39.4)	218(43.6)	110(43.3)	117(47.6)	227(45.4)
Very hard	47(18.5)	38(15.4)	85(17.0)	41(16.1)	46(18.6)	87(17.4)

Table 2.3 showed that 51% and 63% of the adolescents judged respectively paternal and maternal punishment as hard when combining the categories 'a little hard' and 'very hard'.

Findings also showed that more males (66.1%) than females (54.8%) and more females (66.2%) than males (59.4%) judged respectively their paternal and maternal punishment as hard.

Table 2.4

Frequency (%) of responses to "My father/mother punishes me on one occasion for doing something wrong, but s/he doesn't punish me on other occasions for doing the same thing"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Almost always true	61(24.0)	74(30.1)	135(27.0)	51(20.1)	47(19.1)	98(19.6)
Often true	62(24.4)	60(24.4)	122(24.4)	68(26.8)	64(26.0)	132(26.4)
Sometimes true	114(44.9)	74(30.1)	188(37.6)	97(38.2)	100(40.7)	197(39.4)
Almost never true	17(6.7)	38(15.4)	55(11.0)	38(15.0)	35(14.2)	73(14.6)

Table 2.4 showed that both mothers and fathers were not consistent in their punishment behavior. About 89% of adolescents

perceived paternal punishment and 83.6% of them perceived maternal punishment as inconsistent when combining the response

Table 2.5

Frequency (%) of responses to "When I misbehave, I never know from one time to the next if my father/mother will punish me"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Almost always true	59(23.2)	74(30.1)	133(26.6)	48(18.9)	52(21.1)	100(20.0)
Often true	84(33.1)	80(32.5)	164(32.8)	94(37.0)	86(35.0)	180(36.0)
Sometimes true	87(34.2)	66(26.8)	153(30.6)	87(34.3)	68(27.6)	155(31.0)
Almost never true	24(9.4)	26(10.6)	50(10.0)	25(9.8)	40(16.3)	65(13.0)

categories "almost always true", "often true" and "sometimes true". However, the inconsistency was equivalent for males (85%) and females (85.8%) in case of maternal punishment but different in case of paternal punishment (93.3% for males and

84.6% for females).

Table 2.5 showed that 90% and 87% of the adolescents cannot predict whether they will be punished respectively by their fathers and mothers. The picture was similar for sub-samples of males and females.

Table 2.6

Frequency (%) of responses to "On average, my father/mother punishes me time(s) in any give week"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Less than one	101(39.8)	135(54.9)	236(47.2)	64(25.2)	71(28.9)	135(27.0)
One	71(28.0)	46(18.7)	117(23.4)	91(35.8)	69(28.1)	160(32.0)
Two	39(15.4)	37(15.0)	76(15.2)	42(16.5)	50(20.3)	92(18.4)
Three	35(13.8)	21(8.6)	56(11.2)	33(13.0)	44(17.9)	77(15.4)
Four	4(1.7)	5(2.0)	9(1.8)	9(3.5)	2(.8)	11(2.2)
More than Four	4(1.3)	2(.8)	6(1.2)	10(4.0)	10(4.0)	20(4.0)

As can be seen in Table 2.6, about 50% and 75% of the adolescents reported that they received punishment "one or more than one" times in any given week respectively

from their fathers and mothers. The incidence was higher among boys (60.2%) than girls (44.1%) in case of paternal punishment but not of maternal punishment.

Table 2.7

Frequency (%) of responses to "As a general rule, I feel it is when my father/mother punishes me"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Very unfair	28(11.0)	35(14.2)	63(12.6)	33(13.1)	39(15.9)	72(14.4)
A little unfair	52(20.5)	59(24.1)	111(22.2)	57(22.4)	70(28.5)	127(25.4)
A little fair	139(54.7)	114(46.3)	253(50.6)	124(48.8)	100(40.5)	224(44.8)
Very fair	35(13.8)	38(15.4)	73(14.6)	40(15.7)	37(15.1)	77(15.4)

Data displayed in Table 2.7 show that more adolescents judged their parental punishment (65.2% for fathers and 60.2% for mothers) as "fair," when combining the categories "a little fair" and "very fair" compared with who viewed their punishment as "unfair" when combining the categories "a little unfair" and "very unfair" (34.8% for fathers and 39.8% for mothers). The similar picture was observed in case of boys and girls samples as well.

Table 2.8 about here

Table 2.8 showed that vast majority of adolescents felt that they deserved punishment (90% for fathers and 86.8% for mothers) when combining the categories "sometimes", "often" and "almost always" and a very few of them felt that they "almost never" deserved punishment (10% for fathers and 13.2% for mothers). The similar picture was observed separately for boys and girls as well.

Table 2.8

Frequency (%) of responses to "As a general rule, I feel I deserve it when my father/mother punishes me"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Almost never	19(7.5)	31(12.6)	50(10.0)	33(13.0)	33(13.4)	66(13.2)
Sometimes	122(48.0)	119(48.4)	241(48.2)	89(35.0)	104(42.2)	193(38.6)
Often	68(26.8)	56(22.8)	124(24.8)	83(32.7)	70(28.5)	153(30.6)
Almost always	45(17.7)	40(16.2)	85(17.0)	49(19.3)	39(15.9)	88(17.6)

Table 2.9

Frequency (%) of responses to "My father/mother usually punishes me..... when s/he finds out that I did something I wasn't supposed to do. Or when I didn't do something I was supposed to do"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
At the moment	116(45.7)	104(42.3)	220(44.0)	131(51.6)	118(48.0)	249(49.8)
Waits a short while	60(23.6)	43(17.5)	103(20.6)	47(18.5)	44(17.9)	91(18.2)
Waits a long time	30(11.8)	32(13.0)	62(12.4)	39(15.4)	34(13.8)	73(14.6)
Waits a day or more	48(18.9)	67(27.2)	115(23.0)	37(14.5)	50(20.3)	87(17.4)

As appeared in Table 2.9, about half the adolescents reported that they were punished "at the moment" (44% for fathers and 49.8% for mothers) followed

by "waits a short while" (20.6% for fathers and 18.2% for mothers). The similar picture prevailed separately for boys and girls as well.

Table 2.10

Frequency (%) of responses to "Before punishing me, my father/mother explains what I did that was wrong and why it was wrong"

Response options	Paternal Punishment			Maternal Punishment		
	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Almost never true	20(7.9)	35(14.3)	55(11.0)	28(11.1)	34(13.8)	62(12.4)
Sometimes true	59(23.2)	53(21.5)	112(22.4)	75(29.5)	59(24.0)	134(26.8)
Often true	84(33.1)	80(32.5)	164(32.8)	74(29.1)	75(30.5)	149(29.8)
Almost always true	91(35.8)	78(31.7)	169(33.8)	77(30.3)	78(31.7)	155(31.0)

As evident in Table 2.10, majority of the adolescents reported that they were explained before being punished by their parents (89% for fathers and 87.6% for mothers) and a very few of them reported that they were not explained the reasons of their punishment (11% for fathers and 12.4 for mothers). The similar picture prevailed separately for boys and girls as well.

To examine whether there is any significant difference between male and female in their punishment experiences and personality dispositions, we employed independent sample *t* tests. We also computed means and standard deviations of different aspects of punishment and personality dispositions and presented them in Table 3.

 Table 3 about here

As shown in Table 3, significant gender differences were observed in most aspects of paternal punishment. For example, males received a greater variety of punishments than did females (see Table 3). Moreover, males perceived paternal punishments harder than did females. However, no significant gender differences were observed either in maternal punishment or in psychological adjustment.

Results in Table 3 further revealed that on average adolescents reported that they were punished 'occasionally' by their mothers ($M = 2.27$ for girls and $M = 2.70$ for boys) and fathers ($M = 2.87$ for girls and $M = 3.06$ for boys) and when they were punished, it was 'a little hard' ($M = 2.43$ for girls and $M = 2.67$ for boys in case of paternal punishment; $M = 2.67$ for girls and $M = 2.56$ for boys in case of maternal punishment). However, they tended to feel that the physical punishment they received was 'a little fair' and that they 'often' deserved it (see Table 3 for details). Thus, whereas physical punishment was viewed as being slightly harsh overall, it tended to be viewed as being justified. With regard to psychological adjustment, adolescents reported themselves to be fairly psychologically adjusted ($M = 96.97$ for girls and $M = 97.63$ for boys). However, 34% ($N = 170$) of them experienced more psychological maladjustment than adjustment (as defined by scores at or above the child PAQ midpoint of 105).

To test whether there is any significant difference between father and mother in their punishment practices, we computed paired t tests and presented them Table 4.

 Table 4 about here

As can be seen in Table 4, mothers used significantly greater variety of punishments than did fathers ($M = 7.25$ for mothers and $M = 5.85$ for fathers) and maternal punishment was harsher than paternal punishment ($M = 5.57$ for mothers and $M = 5.02$ for fathers). However, no significant gender differences of parents in

severity, fairness, deservedness, use of explanation, and justness of punishments were observed.

To examine whether there is any relation between physical punishment and personality dispositions, we computed Pearson product moment correlations. The results are presented in Table 5.

As evident in Table 5, most aspects of physical punishment are correlated with most of the personality dispositions. For example, the greater the form, frequency, severity, and incidence of punishment experienced by the adolescents at the hands of mothers (and fathers) the more overall psychologically maladjusted, aggressive, and emotionally unresponsive they were; and the more impaired self-esteem, impaired self-adequacy, and negative worldview they had. Furthermore, the more unjust the punishment perceived by the adolescents the more overall psychologically maladjusted and emotionally unresponsive they were; and the more negative worldview they had.

 Table 5 about here

Discussion

The purpose of the present study was mainly to explore possible relations between parental punishment and personality dispositions among adolescent children of Bangladesh. Additionally, it explored parental gender differences in punishment practices and gender differences of children in experiencing punishment and personality dispositions. The results revealed that punishment is related to personality dispositions. Males received more punishment than did females and mothers punished their children more than fathers did. Surprisingly, physical punishment was though viewed as being slightly harsh overall, it tended to be viewed by the adolescents as being justified. The findings of the study are interpreted in the following sections:

Parents in Bangladesh tended to administer mild as well as harsh forms of punishment to discipline their children (see Table 2.1). A vast majority of the children (more than 75%) indicated that their parents used

Table 3

Mean, Standard Deviation, and Independent t for punishment and psychological adjustment

Variable	Girls		Boys		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
<i>Paternal Punishment</i>						
1. Frequency	2.27	1.122	2.70	1.195	4.117	.000
2. Severity	2.43	1.056	2.67	.981	2.712	.007
3. Consistency	2.31	1.061	2.34	.981	.379	.705
4. Predictability	2.18	.982	2.30	.931	1.407	.160
5. Incidence	.88	1.228	1.33	2.524	2.606	.009
6. Fairness	2.63	.911	2.71	.839	1.054	.292
7. Deservedness	2.42	.910	2.55	.869	1.515	.130
8. Time Delay	2.25	1.259	2.04	1.155	-1.969	.050
9. Use of Explanation	2.82	1.036	2.98	.947	1.702	.089
10. Punishment Sum	5.593	2.639	6.090	2.786	2.046	.041
11. Harshness	4.687	1.911	5.334	1.800	3.901	.000
12. Justness	5.04	1.435	5.26	1.396	1.699	.090
<i>Maternal Punishment</i>						
1. Frequency	2.87	1.252	3.06	1.302	1.549	.122
2. Severity	2.67	.978	2.56	.988	-1.315	.189
3. Consistency	2.50	.959	2.48	.977	-.227	.820
4. Predictability	2.39	.655	2.35	.898	-.471	.638
5. Incidence	1.53	1.533	1.63	1.730	.723	.470
6. Fairness	2.56	.925	2.68	.889	1.524	.128
7. Deservedness	2.47	.915	2.58	.945	1.384	.167
8. Time Delay	2.08	1.198	1.93	1.119	-1.352	.177
9. Use of Explanation	2.80	1.037	2.79	.999	-.147	.883
10. Punishment Sum	7.219	3.328	7.271	3.826	.162	.871
11. Harshness	5.540	1.762	5.598	2.008	.341	.733
12. Justness	5.01	1.414	5.25	1.444	1.941	.053
<i>Psychological Adjustment</i>						
1. Aggression	12.6463	3.56756	13.0197	3.65666	1.155	.249
2. Dependence	17.317	3.0541	17.358	2.6853	.160	.873
3. Negative Self-Esteem	12.972	3.2343	13.154	3.2236	.630	.529
4. Negative Self-Adequacy	13.240	3.2254	13.268	3.1821	.097	.923
5. Emotional Unresponsiveness	12.679	3.6127	12.843	3.2521	.533	.594
6. Emotional Instability	15.687	3.0284	15.276	3.2733	-1.458	.146
7. Negative Worldview	12.451	3.7137	12.709	3.6358	.783	.434

slapping as the most common form of punishment. About 25-50% of the children reported that their parents used harsh discipline such as beating and heating as well. However, mothers used on average a greater variety of forms than did fathers to punish their children (See Table 4). The first finding is consistent with a number of international studies (Clawson, Bennett, & Lewis, 2000; Payne, 1989; Rohner, Kean, & Cournoyer, 1991; Roopnarine, Clawson, Bennett, & Lewis, 2000, as reported in Mathurin et al., 2006). The second finding that mothers used a greater variety of forms of punishment is fairly reasonable since they were mostly housewives and hence primary disciplinarians

in our cultural context.

As regards form, frequency, severity, harshness, and incidence males reported to have received higher scores on these dimensions than females in case of paternal punishment (but not maternal). This implies that fathers punished children of same sex more implying that they maintain a double standard for adolescents. In fact, mothers are generally responsible for the discipline of young children and girls. Older boys are believed to be particularly "rough" and therefore in need of a father's discipline. This argument is consistent with the report of Siegal (1987). The author reported that in 20 of 39 independent published studies, the

Table 4*Mean, Standard Deviation, and Paired t for different aspects of physical punishment*

<i>Aspects of Physical Punishment</i>	<i>Fathers</i>		<i>Mothers</i>		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
1. Frequency	2.48	1.18	2.96	1.28	-7.703	.000
2. Severity	2.54	1.03	2.61	.98	-1.252	.211
3. Consistency	2.33	.99	2.49	.97	-3.222	.001
4. Predictability	2.24	.96	2.37	.95	-2.377	.018
5. Incidence	1.05	1.41	1.57	1.63	-6.571	.000
6. Fairness	2.67	.88	2.61	.914	1.240	.216
7. Deservedness	2.49	.89	2.53	.931	-.808	.420
8. Time Delay	2.14	1.21	2.00	1.16	2.289	.022
9. Use of Explanation	2.89	1.00	2.79	1.02	1.741	.082
10. Punishment Sum	5.85	2.72	7.25	3.59	-12.072	.000
11. Harshness	5.02	1.88	5.57	1.89	-5.874	.000
12. Justness	5.15	1.42	5.13	1.43	.272	.786

father's ratings or treatment of boys and girls differed significantly. By contrast, the differences for mothers, if present at all, were comparatively few in any of the studies. The pattern of father-specific effects was most evident in the area of discipline and physical involvement and was weak in the areas of affection and everyday speech with infants and toddlers. Research on children's perceptions of parental socialization behavior is consistent with the existence of differential socialization practices used by the father in particular.

As regards frequency of punishment, mothers punished more often than did fathers (66.8% of mothers and 49.6% of fathers; see Table 2.2 for details). Results of paired *t* test confirmed that mothers punished significantly more often than did fathers (see Table 4). These findings parallel global findings as well as locals. A survey by Bilir, Ari, Donmez, Atik, and San (1991) showed that 88% of children's primary disciplinarians at home were mothers (versus father, 8.2%). Additionally, the study showed that 66% of the unemployed homemaking mothers as opposed to 35% of the working mothers (almost half the homemakers) tended to use corporal

punishment. Related to this is the fact that the use of corporal punishment varied by level of education, with university graduates using corporal punishment least often (34%). UNICEF (2008) also reported that mothers were more likely than fathers or other household members to punish children. In the present study, an overwhelming majority of the respondents' mothers was unemployed housewives (89.2%) as opposed to none of the fathers (0%) was in this occupational group (see Table 1 for details). As a result, mothers more often than fathers had to interact with their children. The homemaking occupation of mothers coupled with their lower level education might have increased frequency of punishment behavior to discipline children. As shown in Table 1, 66% of the mothers had education level lower than Higher Secondary (that included secondary, primary, or no education) and 34% had education level greater than Secondary (that included Higher Secondary, Bachelor, or Masters). On the contrary, 66.8% (almost double the mothers) had education greater than Secondary level (that included Higher Secondary, Bachelor, Masters, Master of Philosophy, Doctor of Philosophy) and 33.2% of the fathers (almost

Table 5
Correlations between different aspects of physical punishment and different personality dispositions (N = 500)

Variable	PAQ	Hostility	Dependency	Negative Self-Esteem	Negative Self-Adequacy	Emotional Unresponsiveness	Emotional Instability	Negative Worldview
Punishment Sum	.260** (.289**)	.274** (.277**)	-.057 (-.083)	.177** (.216**)	.155** (.210**)	.219** (.297**)	.079 (.024)	.178** (.191**)
Harshness	.179** (.218**)	.143** (.165**)	-.105* (-.027)	.126** (.173**)	.118** (.124**)	.191** (.153**)	.055 (.082)	.166** (.187**)
Justness	-.123** (-.125**)	-.046 (-.067)	-.029 (-.016)	-.025 (-.065)	-.089* (-.043)	-.106* (-.141**)	-.069 (-.067)	-.160** (-.101*)
Frequency	.204** (.200**)	.192** (.171**)	-.102* (.011)	.137** (.139**)	.133** (.088*)	.160** (.147**)	.094* (.056)	.182** (.174**)
Severity	.096* (.159**)	.046 (.097*)	-.076 (-.068)	.074 (.153**)	.066 (.122**)	.168** (.103*)	-.004 (.086)	.097* (.132**)
Consistency	.090* (.130**)	.059 (.162**)	-.024 (-.111*)	.072 (.121**)	.049 (.059)	.154** (.117**)	.007 (.067)	.037 (.080)
Predictability	.087 (.083)	.131** (.088)	-.056 (-.006)	.085 (.078)	.081 (.065)	.059 (.072)	-.011 (-.028)	.050 (.062)
Incidence	.182** (.114*)	.153** (.098*)	-.071 (.006)	.121** (.044)	.156** (.083)	.191** (.171**)	.011 (-.021)	.147** (.064)
Fairness	-.126** (-.109*)	-.063 (-.073)	.020 (-.006)	-.051 (-.065)	-.091* (-.033)	-.101* (-.121**)	-.064 (-.080)	-.145** (-.062)
Deservedness	-.085 (-.088*)	-.012 (-.031)	-.062 (-.019)	.013 (-.037)	-.043 (-.035)	-.077 (-.102*)	-.045 (-.021)	-.122* (-.099*)
Delay	.003 (.046)	.015 (.056)	.003 (.049)	-.040 (-.012)	.025 (.031)	.021 (.000)	-.047 (.049)	.025 (.016)
Explanation	-.052 (-.096*)	-.077 (-.059)	.041 (.107)	.012 (-.098*)	-.090* (-.110*)	-.027 (-.101*)	-.016 (-.004)	-.040 (-.099*)

Note. Values in parentheses pertain to mother and outside of it pertain to father
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

half the mothers) had education lower than Higher Secondary level (that included secondary, primary, or no education). This explanation is corroborated by the report of UNICEF (2008) which indicated that parents are less likely to use physical punishment when they have a higher level of education.

As regards severity of punishment, mothers were slightly harsher than fathers. Maternal punishment was perceived hard by 63% of the adolescents whereas paternal punishment was perceived hard by 51% (see Table 2.3). However, paired t test revealed no significant difference between fathers and mothers in severity of their punishment behavior (see Table 4).

As regards consistency and predictability of punishment, both mothers and fathers were found inconsistent and unpredictable indicating that they did not punish all the time the children were found guilty (see Tables 2.4 and 2.5). Paired t test showed that mothers were significantly more consistent and predictable than fathers in punishing their children (see Table 4). These findings are in the expected directions since mothers are the primary disciplinarians, punished children more frequently than fathers and hence more consistent and predictable in their punishment behavior (see Table 2.2).

As regards incidence of punishment, maternal punishment in a given week was 1.5 times higher than paternal punishment (see Table 2.6). This difference was significant at $p < .001$ (see Table 4). Again the finding is in expected direction and compatible with the finding of the present and past studies that mothers more often than fathers punish their children (UNICEF, 2008; Bilir et al., 1991).

Regarding time delay in punishment or immediacy/latency, slightly higher proportion of adolescents reported to have received maternal punishment (50% maternal versus 44% paternal) at the moment when mothers found out that the children did something they were not supposed to do or when they did not do something they were supposed to do (see Table 2.9). Paired t test ascertained that the difference was significant at $p < .05$ (see Table 4). This finding that mothers more

immediately punished their children is embedded again in the same source that mothers are the primary disciplinarians and they administered punishment more frequently than did fathers.

The correlations between punishment and personality dispositions were significant. As shown in Table 5, the more the form, frequency, severity, and incidence of the punishments experienced by the adolescents at the hands of mothers (and fathers) the more overall psychologically maladjusted, aggressive, and emotionally unresponsive they were; and the more impaired self-esteem, impaired self-adequacy, and negative worldview they had. Similarly, the more unjust the punishments perceived by the adolescents the more overall psychologically maladjusted and emotionally unresponsive they were; and the more negative worldview they had. These findings are consistent with many past studies (Erkman & Rohner, 2006; Steely & Rohner, 2006; Mathurin et al., 2006).

Even though adolescents perceived their punishment hard they judged that they deserved it. More than half of the adolescents reported that they frequently received different forms of punishment and they perceived their punishment hard (see Tables 2.2 & 2.3). Moreover, more than half considered punishment to be fair and vast majority of them felt that they deserved it (see Tables 2.7 & 2.8). It is plausible that cultural norms of Bangladesh favoring the use of corporal punishment may have caused many youths to accept physical punishment as appropriate and hence tolerable even when the punishment is severe. In this way, youths may have come to learn that punishment is a part of normal upbringing. This may be compared to findings that the youths of St. Kitts, West Indies, believed "beatings" were a good and proper way of raising children (see Rohner, Kean, & Cournoyer, 1991, as reported in Mathurin et al., 2006). This apparent paradox that adolescents perceived punishment harsh on the one hand and viewed punishment justified on the other hand has implication for parents, teachers, counselors, and other relevant professionals especially in the cultural context of Bangladesh.

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